

The effects of risk committee characteristics on bank asset quality

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Abstract

This paper examines the influence of risk committee characteristics on the asset quality of 21 banks in Nigeria for 2013-2022. Previous studies have largely ignored this nexus and presented defective results. However, this study uses data from 21 banks from Nigeria over a period of 10 years (from year 2013 to 2022). The study finds that, in general, risk committee characteristics positively influence asset quality and its individual components (except risk committee gender and meetings). The results show that there are differences in the role risk committees play in influencing asset quality in Nigeria. Thus, this study highlights the importance of risk committee in strengthening firm's asset quality. The study also highlights the need to assess risk committee characteristics separately, in addition to the overall component, when conducting studies on the role of risk committee in asset quality of banks. Furthermore, regulators, shareholders, lenders, boards of directors, etc. would benefit from the findings of this paper. Note that these findings are restricted to banks in emerging economies as the results may vary in developed economies. Also, the results are valid based on the variables used and period coverage.

Keywords: *Asset Quality, Banks, Characteristics, Nigeria, Risk Committee*

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Introduction

Risk committee is one of the board of directors' committees and is part of corporate governance mechanisms, plays an essential role in asset quality of companies globally. The risk committee is an independent committee of the Board of Directors that has, as its sole and exclusive function, responsibility

for the oversight of the risk management policies and practices of a company's operations. A risk committee is an important part of risk governance across the firm. At the corporate level, the risk committee is there to assist the board with strategic risk management. For some companies, risk is one of the responsibilities of the audit committee. However, for proper delineation of responsibilities, risk oversight is the responsibility of board's risk committee except in its absence. Furthermore, the purpose of the risk committee is to assist the Board in its oversight of management's responsibility to implement an effective risk management systems, designed to identify, assess and manage the firm's strategic, credit and investment, market, and operational risks. Its responsibilities include approval of applicable primary risk policies and review of certain associated frameworks, analysis and reporting established by management. The risk committee oversees credit risks, otherwise also known as asset quality.

In this paper, risk committee characteristics are operationalized via risk committee presence, risk committee size, risk committee independence, risk committee gender diversity and risk committee meetings. Furthermore, asset quality (credit risk) is operationalized via non-performing loan (NPL, Beck et al., 2015). A nonperforming loan (NPL) is a loan in which the borrower is in default and has not made any scheduled payments of principal or interest for a certain period of time. In banking, loans are considered nonperforming if the borrower is 90 days past due. Non-performing loans occur when borrowers run out of money to make repayments or get into situations that make it difficult for them to continue making repayments towards the loan.

Asset quality (nonperforming loan) is a reflection of the quantity of existing and potential credit risk associated with loans and investment portfolios, real estate assets owned, and other assets, as well as off-balance sheet transactions of a bank, and as such, essential to the operations of a bank. Loans granted to businesses and households are assets for banks. The interest banks earn on these assets is a key component of their income and profit, and the risk of the loans not being paid back is their main risk. The higher this credit risk, the lower the quality of the loan, or asset quality. In view of the collapse of banks in Nigeria in recent years, there is no gainsaying that banks' asset quality requires further interrogation. This is the motivation of this paper. In this paper, asset quality is proxy by the amount of NPL of firm i over year t .

Banks are financial intermediaries bridging the gap between the surplus and deficit sectors. They are essential to the health of any economy, Nigeria is inclusive. A bank is a financial institution that is licensed to accept cheques and savings deposits and create credits (loans). Banks also provide related services such as individual retirement accounts (IRAs), certificates of deposit (CDs), currency exchange, and safe deposit boxes. There are several types of banks including retail banks, mortgage banks, savings and loans banks, commercial or corporate banks, and investment banks.

In Nigeria, banks are allowed to operate universal banking system, which allows the group to operate subsidiaries in other similar financial services. For example, First Bank of Nigeria Plc now operates as FBN Holdings Plc; Access Bank Plc now operates as Access Holdings Plc; FCMB now operates as FCMB Group Plc and GTB now operates as Guaranty Trust Holdings Company Plc, etc. The Nigerian banking industry contributed ₦168.4 trillion to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) between 2017 and 2020, indicating an incredible resilience and growth, despite two difficult recessions as the sector contributed about ₦34.6 trillion to the country's GDP in 2017; ₦37.8 trillion in 2018; ₦42.7 trillion in 2019; and ₦53.3 trillion in 2020 (Ailemen, 2022).

Banks have existed since at least the 14th century. They provide a safe place for individuals and businesses to store their cash and a source of loans for personal purchases and business ventures. In turn, the banks use the cash that is deposited to make loans and collect interest on them. The basic business plan has remained fundamentally ever since, but of course, the range of products and services that banks offer has grown. Banks offer 3 basic services to customers in order to stash their cash and various ways to borrow money: chequing services, savings and loans services. The banking sector has a pivotal role in the development of an economy. It is the key driver of economic growth of the country. Various literature revealed that non-performing loans were one of the causes of the financial crisis in 2007. The rise in non-performing loans has been taken under consideration by many banks in the world, as banks look at different methods on how to reduce non-performing loans.

The remainder of the paper is organized into four sections. Section 2 presents literature review, covering both conceptual, theoretical and empirical literature. Section 3 presents the methodology, covering research design, population and sample, sources and methods of data collection, analyses and post estimations diagnostics. Section 4 presents the descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and regression results. Section 5 presents the conclusions, drawn based on the empirical results and offers both policy and performance improvement recommendations.

Literature Review

Non-Performing Loan (NPL) is one of the concrete embodiments of credit risk which banks take. NPL is a huge puzzle for Chinese commercial banks, so how to enhance risk management to improve assets quality and lower down NPL are of great importance to those banks. Generally, the majority of empirical studies examining the role of risk committee characteristics in asset quality have defined asset quality primarily within loan loss provision and used it to measure or as proxy for asset quality (Manukaji, 2018; Ozili, 2015, 2017, 2019; Ozili & Outas, 2019). Few studies seek to analyze the association between risk committee characteristics and asset quality within the context of nonperforming loan. Generally, non-performing loans are considered bad debts because the chances of recovering the defaulted loan repayments are minimal. However, having more non-performing loans in the company's balance hurts the bank's cash flows, as well as its stock price. Therefore, banks that have non-performing loans in their books may take action to enforce

the recovery of the loans they are owed. When a bank records a large percentage of its outstanding loans as non-performing loans, it can hurt the asset quality of the bank. Banks mainly make money from the interest they charge on loans, and when they are unable to collect the owed interest payments from NPLs, it means that they will have less money available to create new loans and pay operating costs. The money represents an income that is potentially lost, and it affects the profitability of the bank. Not only does it affect the bank, but it also leaves potential borrowers with fewer options to get loans from the bank. Holding a high number of NPLs relative to the total assets of a bank poses a huge risk to the bank. Potential investors are interested in investing in banks with healthy books of accounts. When the percentage of non-performing loans increases, the bank's share price will also go down. The NPLs a bank holds in its books, the less attractive it is for potential investors because its future profitability will suffer if the bank will not earn an income from its credit business. Furthermore, the bank will be required to set aside a portion of its profits as bad debts provisions in case it is required to write off the debts.

Risk committee presence refers to the existence of a risk committee. In some companies, the functions of risk committee are carried out by the audit committee. However, this is not ideal for the purpose of ensuring good corporate governance, also, risk committee size refers to the number of members of the risk committee of the company. In the instant case, we refer to the number of directors on the risk committee. In addition, risk committee independence refers to the proportion of independent directors to total directors on the risk committee. Furthermore, risk committee gender simply refers to the proportion of women relative to the size of the risk committee. Finally, risk committee meetings refer to the number of times risk committee members hold meetings in a year.

This paper is anchored on the agency theory. The theory was propounded by Jensen and Meckling (1976). The main point of Jensen's and Meckling (1976) model is that there is a tradeoff in the form of agency costs between having more or less insider ownership. Agency costs are created whenever the manager also controls an outsider's investment besides her own, because there is a fundamental conflict of interest. Risk committee members are members of the board of directors of a company, they would have pecuniary interests in the businesses of the company. This is exactly the conflict of interests that agency theory tries to solve by reminding risk committee members that they exist only to protect the interests of owners and not their own interests.

In terms of empirics, a few number of scholarly works have examined the nexus between risk committee characteristics and asset quality. For example, Haneef et al. (2012) investigate the impact of risk management on non-performing loan of banking sector of Pakistan. The result of this study reveals that there is no proper mechanism for risk management in banking sector of Pakistan. Study also concluded that non-performing loans are increasing due to lack of risk management which threatens the asset quality of banks. Furthermore, Ben-Saada (2018) explores the extent to which the risk committee impacts non-performing loans (NPLs) of Tunisian listed banks. The results show that the risk committee is more effective than the other committees in reducing non-performing loans.

Adegboye et al. (2020) examine the sensitivity of non-performing loans and corporate governance structure. From the empirical analysis, corporate governance structure of banks in Nigeria has a negative and significant influence on non-performing loans in Nigerian banks. This result reveals that sound corporate governance structure enhances the loan quality and bank stability. Islam (2020) examines the impact of board composition and activity on bank nonperforming loans (NPLs). The empirical evidence suggests that NPLs are negatively related to risk committee independence, and the frequency of risk committee meetings. Furthermore, Khairi et al. (2021) determine the factors associated with non-performing loans. They identify several variables that affect NPLs and those that are influenced by NPLs. They found no variables that associate with NPLs.

Maseke and Swartz (2021) analyze the impact of risk management on non-performing loans in Namibia and identifying different strategies used around the world that assists banks in battling non-performing loans. The study found that the Namibian banks experienced an increase throughout the five years in both profits and non-performing loans. Furthermore, Karaye et al. (2022) evaluate the effect of risk committee characteristics on bank asset quality in Nigeria risk committee independence, size, meetings, gender, expertise and their influence on non-performing loans. The study finds that risk committee independence and risk committee size have a significant negative relation while risk committee gender, risk committee meetings have significant positive relations with non-performing loans.

Also, Kartika et al. (2022) conclude that risk committee independence is needed to stabilize and even minimize non-performing loans in banks' 440 annual financial statements of emerging markets sourced from Bloomberg during 2016–2020. Tarchouna et al. (2022) study the ability of the corporate governance of banks to reduce non-performing loans. The dynamic panel GMM estimation is applied to 184 US commercial banks over 2000–2013 period. The central finding of this research is that small banks are characterized by a weak and fragile corporate governance system which leads to a bad loan quality. Concerning medium banks, they notice a sound corporate governance system. As far as large banks are concerned, it is to mention that the corporate governance system of these banks is neutralized.

Based on these empirics, the following hypotheses are formulated and test:

H₁: Risk committee presence has no significant effect on asset quality.

H₂: Risk committee size has no significant effect on asset quality.

H₃: Risk committee independence has no significant effect on asset quality.

H₄: Risk committee gender has no significant effect on asset quality.

H₅: Risk committee meetings have no significant effect on asset quality.

Methodology

The NGX 21 listed banks constitute the population and sample of the study. These companies accounted for more than 42.86 percent (21/49) of listed financial services companies as on 29 July 2023. The data for our analysis is sourced from the NGX website (<https://ngxgroup.com/exchange/trade/equities/listed->

companies). We examine the effect of risk committee characteristics on asset quality using the following model, adapted from Beck et al. (2015):

$$AQ_{i,t} = \alpha + RCP_{i,t}\beta_1 + RCS_{i,t}\beta_2 + RCI_{i,t}\beta_3 + RCG_{i,t}\beta_4 + RCM_{i,t}\beta_5 + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas:

AQ = Asset quality, measured as nonperforming loan by bank *i* at time *t*.

RCP = Risk committee presence, measured as a dummy 1, if there is risk committee in *i* at year *t*, otherwise 0.

RCS = Risk committee size, measured as is the total directors and non-directors in the risk committee.

RCI = Risk committee independence, measured as the number of non-directors and non-executive directors in the risk committee divided by risk committee members size (%).

RCG = Risk committee gender, measured as the number of female risk committee members divided by risk committee members size (%).

RCM = Risk committee meetings, measured as number of meetings held by the risk committee members in a year.

β_{1-5} = Beta coefficients to be estimated by a process of regression.

ε = Idiosyncratic error term

i = Firm scripts (*i* = 21 firms)

t = Time script (*t* = 10 years)

Consistent with the previous literature, we use nonperforming loan as a measure of asset quality as used by Beck et al. (2015). As in the literature, we consider the nonperforming loan as a proxy for the state of asset quality. High absolute value of NPL indicates low asset quality and vice versa. As discussed earlier, risk committee can potentially have both positive and negative effects on asset quality. However, as per our hypotheses, we predict that risk committee characteristics do not have significant effects on asset quality. Although, we are investigating how risk committee characteristics can influence the extent of asset quality, there are other firm level factors that can influence asset quality and which require to be controlled for in the estimations. On the basis of earlier studies, we initially consider firm size, firm listing age, firm leverage, and firm market share as the control variable. However, the model specification linktest results in Table 7 indicate that the model is well specified without the control variables. Thus, the control variables of the paper were dropped completely from the model. Furthermore, we use the GMM model, which is generally used for panel data, and which usually provides consistent results in the presence of different sources of endogeneity (Wintoki et al., 2012)

Empirical Results and Discussions

As mentioned in methodology section, our sample consists of the 21 listed banks that trade on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange, accounting for about 42.85 percent of financial services companies. Summary measures (descriptive statistics) of variables of interest are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
AQ	210	-6.108	43.518	-494.019	50.276
RCP	210	.985	.124	0	1
RCS	210	6.946	2.314	0	14
RCI	210	64.502	18.615	0	100
RCG	210	15.712	15.913	0	66.667
RCM	210	4.123	1.604	0	9

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Table 1 shows that the number of observations is 210, which consists of the 21 banks at 10 years coverage. Furthermore, the average of AQ is -6.108, with a standard deviation of 43.518, which is extremely higher than the average, suggesting that AQ is of concern and requires investigation. Also, AQ has minimum and maximum values of -494.019 and 50.276, respectively. In contrast, RCP has a mean of .985 percent, suggesting that about 99 percent of the banks have risk committee. It also have a lower standard deviation of .124, suggesting that its volatility is low. It has a minimum mean of 0, suggesting that some banks do not have risk committee; it has a maximum mean of 1, which indicates the presence of risk committee. In the same vein, RCS has a mean of 10 members, with a standard deviation of 2 members, meaning that the volatility is low.

In addition, it shows a minimum mean of 0, suggesting that some banks do not a separate risk committee and maximum mean of 14 members. Furthermore, Table 1 shows that RCI has an average of 64.502 percent, with a standard deviation of 18.615 percent, which is lower than the mean, suggesting that it is not volatile. It also shows a minimum mean of 0, which implies that some banks do not have risk committee. It further shows a maximum mean of 100 percent, suggesting that all the members of risk committee are non-executive directors as required by Corporate Governance Code 2018. Table 1 also shows that the mean of RCG is 15.712 percent, mean that about 16 percent of the banks have at least a women in their risk committee. The standard deviation is 15.913 percent, which is higher than the mean, suggesting that there is a small variability in the inclusion of women in some of the banks' risk committee. RCM shows an average of 4 meetings per year as required by law, with a standard deviation of about 2 meetings. The minimum mean of RCM is 0, for those banks that do not have a separate risk committee and 9 times for some of the banks.

Furthermore, a number of diagnostic tests are provided in order to ensure that the model that is reported is best linear unbiased estimator. These diagnostic tests include normality of residuals, heteroskedasticity of residuals, multicollinearity test among the independent variables, model specification error test, Table 2 reports the results of normality of residuals test.

Table 2

Results of normality of residuals test

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

The results in Table 2 without any doubt shows that the model is not normally distributed. Therefore, the final model of this study would require a robustness treatment. Furthermore, we carry out a check for heteroskedasticity of residuals. Table 3 reports the results of the test.

Table 3

Results of heteroskedasticity of residuals

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

The rule of engagement when it comes to heteroskedasticity test is that there should be no pattern in a plot of residuals and fitted values. As shown in Table 3, both residuals and fitted values lie on a linear line, suggesting that there is heteroskedasticity problem in the model. Table 4 provides statistical evidence to support this claim.

Table 4

Results of heteroskedasticity test

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Ho: Constant variance

Variables: fitted values of AQ

Chi²(1) = 147.03Prob > chi² = 0.0000

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Table 4 indicates clearly that the model has heteroskedasticity problem and requires robustness treatment. We also carry out a multicollinearity test via variance inflation factors (VIF) and the results are reported in Table 5.

Table 5

Results of multicollinearity test

	VIF	1/VIF
RCI	1.946	.514
RCP	1.941	.515
RCS	1.809	.553
RCM	1.376	.727
RCGD	1.079	.927
Mean VIF	1.566	.

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

The results in Table 5 show that there is no multicollinearity among the risk committee characteristics and listing age. In order to confirm these results, a correlation matrix is produced as indicated in Table 6.

Table 6

Correlation Matrix

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
(1) AQ	1.000					
(2) RCP	-0.001 (0.989)	1.000				
(3) RCS	-0.009 (0.918)	0.377* (0.000)	1.000			
(4) RCI	0.026 (0.767)	0.435* (0.000)	- (0.001)	1.000		
(5) RCGD	-0.005 (0.955)	0.124 (0.160)	0.108 (0.222)	0.014 (0.872)	1.000	
(6) RCM	0.115 (0.192)	0.322* (0.000)	-0.069 (0.434)	0.441* (0.000)	0.132 (0.134)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

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Pearson correlations reported in Table 6 do not exceed .435. Also the variance inflation factor (VIF) values (calculated with every multiple regression model performed) not exceed 3.00. All VIF values are substantially below the critical value of 10.00 (Yu et al., 2015). Based on Pearson correlations and VIF values, multicollinearity does not appear to be a serious concern. We further carry out model specification test and the results of the test are reported in Table 7.

Table 7

Results of Linktest

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs = 210		
Model	10017.847	2	5008.923	Prob>F = .07		
Residual	2.34e+05	127	1844.718	R-squared = 0.041		
Total	2.44e+05	129	1893.776	Root MSE = 42.950		

AQ	Coef.	Std.Err.	t	P>t	[95%Conf. Interval]	
_hat	0.321	0.728	0.440	0.660	-1.120	1.762
_hatsq	-0.083	0.052	-1.610	0.109	-0.186	0.019
_cons	2.319	5.426	0.430	0.670	-8.417	13.056

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

As indicated in Table 7, the p-value of linktest is not significant for _hatsq, suggesting that the model is well specified. The core research question in this paper is to assess whether risk committee characteristics lead to lower loan loss provision or higher. The answers can be found in regression table (Table 8).

Table 8

Regression Results

AQ	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P>z	[95% Conf. Interval]
/xb_RCP	-30.81493	14.6907	-2.10	0.036	-2.0217 59.60817
/xb_RCS	-1.97515	1.040211	-1.90	0.058	-4.013925 .0636256
/xb_RCI	-.2024848	.1079961	-1.87	0.061	-.4141533 .0091838
/xb_RCGD	-.1023544	.0695386	-1.47	0.141	-.2386476 .0339389
/xb_RCM	-1.010752	.9077233	-1.11	0.265	-.7683531 2.789857
/b0	2.8202	1.14021	2.47	0.013	.5854301 5.05497

Number of parameters = 6

Number of moments = 6

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 210

GMM weight matrix: Robust

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

The GMM model, which is generally used for panel data, provides consistent results in the presence of different sources of endogeneity, namely unobserved heterogeneity, simultaneity and dynamic endogeneity (Wintoki et al., 2012). Table 8 shows that RCP has a negative and significant effect on asset quality (proxy by NPL) at 5 percent. These results are consistent with our *a priori* expectation and previous literature.

Similarly, RCS shows a negative and significant effect on asset quality at 10 percent. Furthermore, RCI shows a negative and significant effect on asset quality at 10 percent. These results are also consistent with extant literature and our *a priori* expectation. We failed to find any significance for risk committee gender and meetings.

Conclusions and Recommendations

We have examined the effects of risk committee characteristics on asset quality of banks in Nigeria. While risk committee characteristics were proxy by risk committee presence, risk committee size, risk committee independence, risk committee gender, and risk committee meetings; asset quality was measured by nonperforming loans, that is, there is inverse relationship between asset quality and nonperforming loans. The research design was correlational research design. The source of data was the NGX and the methods of analyses include descriptive analysis, diagnostic analysis, correlation analysis, and generalized methods of moments. The results of descriptive analysis show clearly that asset quality is highly invariable, therefore, it requires further studies. The results of diagnostic tests show that the model is not normally distributed, there is presence of heteroskedasticity of residuals, and there is no multicollinearity among the independent variables. Furthermore, it shows that the model is well specified as indicated in Table 7. The results of GMM regression analysis show that only RCP, RCS and RCI significantly reduces NPL, which was used to proxy asset quality. However, we failed to find similar effects for RCG and RCM on asset quality.

We thus conclude that in Nigeria, only RCP, RCS and RCI are the determinants of banks' asset quality. We therefore, recommends (1) that banks should take measures to establish risk committee (2) to ensure that the risk committee members are up to a minimum of 3 members (3) are majorly made up of non-executive directors. There is no gainsaying that this paper faces some limitations (1) the study data is limited to 2013 to 2022 (2) risk committees are proxy by risk committee presence, size, independence, gender and meetings (3) the results are limited to banks. Further studies may extend the sector to include insurance sector where asset quality is measured similarly. Despite these limitations, regulators, shareholders, lenders, boards of directors, etc. would benefit from the findings of this paper.

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